

Dose	Species	Sr/Ca		Sr/Ca		Sr/Ca		Na/Ca		Na/Ca		Na/Ca		Mg/Ca		Mg/Ca		Mg/Ca	
		peak		mean		background		peak		mean		background		peak		mean		background	
		[mmol/mol]		[mmol/mol]		[mmol/mol]		[mmol/mol]		[mmol/mol]		[mmol/mol]		[mmol/mol]		[mmol/mol]		[mmol/mol]	
High	<i>M. edulis</i>	1.02	± 0.43	0.45	± 0.16	0.41	± 0.09	5.27	± 1.59	3.06	± 0.85	2.99	± 0.70	2.49	± 2.45	1.04	± 0.84	0.83	± 0.28
	<i>O. edulis</i>	0.84	± 0.86	0.23	± 0.09	0.23	± 0.08	145.15	± 291.04	10.40	± 13.38	16.11	± 29.35	28.30	± 40.84	3.37	± 3.46	4.14	± 6.10
	<i>C. edule</i>	1.57	± 0.81	0.81	± 0.26	0.56	± 0.31	10.26	± 2.46	6.88	± 1.90	6.83	± 1.95	0.43	± 0.23	0.30	± 0.11	0.29	± 0.11
	N	36		36		36		18		18		18		36		36		36	
	mean	1.36	± 0.81	0.65	± 0.32	0.48	± 0.28	53.56	± 171.35	6.78	± 7.97	8.64	± 16.93	5.42	± 18.64	0.94	± 1.76	1.02	± 2.72
Medium	<i>M. edulis</i>	0.62	± 0.04	0.33	± 0.02	0.30	± 0.04	6.92	± 0.83	4.06	± 0.43	4.00	± 0.42	1.45	± 0.06	0.90	± 0.03	0.92	± 0.12
	<i>O. edulis</i>	0.33	± 0.08	0.20	± 0.02	0.20	± 0.03	6.58	± 0.36	4.01	± 0.20	3.97	± 0.26	2.76	± 0.06	1.35	± 0.17	1.36	± 0.19
	<i>C. edule</i>	0.62	± 0.24	0.46	± 0.08	0.42	± 0.07	9.75	± 2.45	6.66	± 1.43	6.76	± 1.19	0.70	± 0.27	0.48	± 0.12	0.41	± 0.10
	N	15		15		15		9		9		9		15		15		15	
	mean	0.56	± 0.22	0.38	± 0.13	0.35	± 0.11	7.75	± 2.00	4.91	± 1.51	4.91	± 1.53	1.26	± 0.85	0.74	± 0.38	0.70	± 0.41
Low	<i>M. edulis</i>	0.52	± 0.02	0.29	± 0.01	0.26	± 0.02	6.53	± 0.43	3.69	± 0.29	3.59	± 0.21	2.11	± 0.42	1.26	± 0.32	1.09	± 0.21
	<i>O. edulis</i>	0.36	± 0.17	0.20	± 0.06	0.19	± 0.05	13.76	± 16.95	5.04	± 2.19	4.26	± 0.80	4.15	± 2.93	1.94	± 0.85	1.57	± 0.44
	<i>C. edule</i>	0.82	± 0.26	0.53	± 0.08	0.44	± 0.06	9.15	± 1.86	6.62	± 1.40	6.64	± 1.35	0.62	± 0.26	0.43	± 0.09	0.44	± 0.11
	N	19		19		19		15		15		15		19		19		19	
	mean	0.63	± 0.30	0.39	± 0.17	0.33	± 0.13	10.47	± 10.61	5.40	± 1.94	5.08	± 1.64	1.97	± 2.24	1.04	± 0.84	0.90	± 0.58
Dose	Species	Mn/Ca		Mn/Ca		Mn/Ca		Ba/Ca		Ba/Ca		Ba/Ca							
		peak		mean		background		peak		mean		background							
		[μmol/mol]		[μmol/mol]		[μmol/mol]		[μmol/mol]		[μmol/mol]		[μmol/mol]							
High	<i>M. edulis</i>	24.49	± 20.19	9.26	± 2.74	14.32	± 14.03	0.96	± 0.51	0.41	± 0.18	0.44	± 0.24						
	<i>O. edulis</i>	1295	± 2043	87	± 135	116	± 262	216	± 343	7	± 10.04	4.17	± 9.77						
	<i>C. edule</i>	3.73	± 2.46	2.17	± 0.71	2.15	± 0.74	1.48	± 1.06	0.87	± 0.50	0.81	± 0.35						
	N	36		36		36		36		36		36							
	mean	222	913	± 17	60	± 23	108	± 37	153	± 2	± 4.43	1.31	± 3.93						
Medium	<i>M. edulis</i>	19.10	± 3.95	9.38	± 2.10	10.03	± 1.62	0.47	± 0.12	0.21	± 0.03	0.21	± 0.04						
	<i>O. edulis</i>	38.47	± 48.83	7.65	± 4.72	5.04	± 0.15	0.78	± 0.78	0.11	± 0.06	0.10	± 0.03						
	<i>C. edule</i>	19.11	± 23.55	5.53	± 5.26	3.00	± 2.25	1.48	± 0.75	0.80	± 0.38	0.66	± 0.33						
	N	15		19		19		19		19		19							
	mean	22.98	± 26.91	6.72	± 4.71	4.82	± 3.35	1.14	± 0.78	0.54	± 0.44	0.46	± 0.36						
Low	<i>M. edulis</i>	12.99	± 2.53	6.09	± 1.30	7.29	± 1.55	0.45	± 0.10	0.19	± 0.03	0.18	± 0.04						
	<i>O. edulis</i>	23.51	± 16.48	6.14	± 2.22	5.28	± 2.06	0.75	± 0.53	0.11	± 0.04	0.07	± 0.04						
	<i>C. edule</i>	5.22	± 5.37	2.10	± 1.00	2.26	± 1.23	1.23	± 0.53	0.66	± 0.37	0.67	± 0.34						
	N	19		19		19		15		15		15							
	mean	12.22	± 12.66	4.01	± 2.51	4.01	± 2.50	0.95	± 0.56	0.41	± 0.38	0.40	± 0.38						